

CoEvolution

4th Press Release

CoEvolution Project Announces the **1st Workshop on Secure and Intelligent Data Spaces**

The **CoEvolution** project is pleased to announce the **1st Workshop on Secure and Intelligent Data Spaces (SIDS 2026)**, a scientific event dedicated to advancing research and innovation in secure, trustworthy, and intelligent data-sharing infrastructures.

The workshop will take place on **29 June 2026 in Athens, Greece**, as part of the **27th IEEE International Conference on Mobile Data Management (MDM 2026)**. It will bring together researchers, practitioners, and industry experts to explore emerging challenges and solutions for building secure and intelligent data spaces.

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Call for Contributions

Researchers and practitioners are invited to submit their work and contribute to shaping the future of secure data ecosystems.

Important Dates

- **Paper submission deadline:**... 27 March 2026
- **Notification of acceptance:**..... 15 April 2026
- **Camera-ready papers:**..... 15 May 2026
- **Workshop date:**..... 29 June 2026

More information about the workshop, topics, and submission guidelines can be found on the official event page.

Contact & Further Information

Learn more about the workshop and the CoEvolution project:

Consortium

CoEvolution is a 3-year project, coordinated by **Erevnitiko Panepistimiako Institutou Systematon Epikoinonion Kai Ypologiston**, and composed of **15 partners from 8 countries**.

SIEMENS

AEGIS
IT RESEARCH

Telefónica
Innovación Digital

Stay informed on CoEvolution's progress and explore project updates, publications, and events at www.coevolution-project.eu

Follow CoEvolution Project on social media platforms